

Train the Trainer: In-person edition in Arecibo (Puerto Rico)

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Between January 14 and 16, 2026, we delivered an in-person edition of our [Train the Trainer](#) course at the Arecibo C3 STEM Center (Puerto Rico). The course was free of charge and taught in Spanish. It was aimed at people who teach (or want to teach) programming and data science.

What we worked on during the course

[Train the Trainer](#) is designed to support Spanish-speaking communities in developing practical teaching skills. The goal is to help multiply learning and strengthen collective impact.

During the course, we worked on (among other topics):

- Identifying levels of prior knowledge and mental models in an audience.
- Designing lessons with clear objectives and simple exercises to avoid cognitive overload.
- Building safe and open learning environments.
- Practicing live coding with clarity.
- Giving and receiving feedback to improve teaching and learning.

The program responds to a common need: many people with strong disciplinary expertise have not had formal training in effective teaching. We can facilitate the course in both online and in-person formats.

About the program

Before visiting Arecibo, we updated the content and activities of our [Train the Trainer](#). The new materials are openly licensed and available to explore, reuse, and adapt at:

<https://metadocencia.github.io/formacion/>

This is our first course using MetaDocencia's course template, adapted from The Carpentries' [Workbench](#). The program draws on and connects with similar open initiatives such as [The Carpentries Instructor Training](#), the Train the Trainer courses from [ELIXIR-GOBLET](#) and [EMBL-EBI](#), and [Greg Wilson's](#) book [Teaching Tech Together](#).

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